

Tiling Finite Planes

Jalal Khairabadi *

Department of Computer and Information Sciences
Institute for Advanced Studies in Basic Sciences
Zanjan, Iran
j.khair@iasbs.ac.ir

Rebvar Hosseini

Department of Computer and Information Sciences
Institute for Advanced Studies in Basic Sciences
Zanjan, Iran
r.hosseini@iasbs.ac.ir

Bahram Sadeghi Bigham

Department of Computer and Information Sciences
Institute for Advanced Studies in Basic Sciences
Zanjan, Iran
b.sadeghi_b@iasbs.ac.ir

Zohreh Mohammad Alizadeh

Department of Computer and Information Sciences
Institute for Advanced Studies in Basic Sciences
Zanjan, Iran
z.alizadeh@iasbs.ac.ir

Abstract: A set of natural numbers tiles the plane if a square-tiling of the plane exists using exactly one square of side length n for every n in the set. From [2] we know that $\mathbb{N}$ itself tiles the plane. From that and [3] we know that the set of even numbers tiles the plane while the set of odd numbers does not. According to [1] it is possible to tile the plane using only an odd square. Also it is possible to tile the plane using exactly three odd squares, but it is impossible to tile the plane using exactly 2 odd numbers. In this paper we will check that there exists a finite set containing $n \neq 3$ odd numbers and a set of even numbers that can tile a finite plane.

Keywords: Tiling; Plane; Finite Set; Finite Plane; Fibonacci.

1 Introduction

In 1903, M. Behn [4] asked: Is it possible to tile a square with smaller squares, such that no square is the same size? In 1925, Moron found several rectangles that can be tiled with squares [9]. Dehn's question was answered by R. Sprague's [10] confirmation. The question and its answer was the disputable subject of a paper, "squaring an square" by Tutte [11], and was reprinted in Scientific American by Martin Gardner [12]. Several papers have been presented in this subject ever since [5-7]. In 1975, Golomb [8] asked if it is possible to tile an infinite plane using different squares with every side-length represented. In 1907, Karl Scherer [13] was assisted in tiling the plane using squares with integral sides, but in different sizes. The number of squares used with n side, $t(n)$, is finite, but the function t is not limited. Golomb's question was answered confirmatively in "squaring the square" [2]. The solution presented

caused plenty of questions, for example, which sets can tile the plane? Is it possible to tile without squared rectangles? Is there three-coloured tiling? Is it possible to tile a half-plane?

The second paper [3] showed that no set of odd numbers and primes can tile the plane. This paper found a kind of tiling without squared rectangles. It showed that the set of natural numbers can tile many even infinite pages. But it caused many questions. Can a superset of a tiling set tile the plane? Is it possible to partition $\mathbb{N}$ into two tiling and non-tiling sets? Is it possible to tile Riemann Plane?

There are some relationships between squared planes and squared squares. Thus, there are some strange disconnects. It can be proved that it is not possible to cube a cube [11]. But it has not been presented that it is not possible to cube the plane.

*Corresponding Author, P. O. Box 45195-1159, M: (+98) 918 998-4279, T: (+98) 241 415-5056

2 Tiling Finite Planes

In this section, we will review tiling for various scenarios. Suppose that a set of even numbers is presented. In this section, the purpose is to tile a finite plane with this set of even numbers and 1 or 2 odd numbers.

2.1 Set With One or Two Odd Number

2.1.1 Proposition 1

Definition: A set containing just one odd number can tile the plane. **Proof:** Here the even numbers set is empty.

Consider a square with an odd side length. Another square with the same side length can tile this square. For example a square with side length 5 can be tiled with another square with the same side length.

By [1] we know that a set containing just two odd numbers and a set of evens can not tile an infinite plane, so we have the following proposition:

Figure 1: Integral Side

2.1.2 Proposition 2

Definition: A set containing exactly two odd numbers and a set of evens can not tile a finite plane. To prove this proposition the following definition is needed.

Definition: At every corner of a square s there is an edge extending away from s . We will call such a line a spoke of S . We will say that s has an integral side, if it has two spokes extending in parallel from adjacent corners. If s has no integral side we say it is a Pin-wheel (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Plane with 2 even-value tile

Figure 3: Tiling Example, 32×33

Proof : The finite plane is in two different states from one point of view :

1. At least, one of the sides is even.
2. Or, both sides are odd.

Proof 1 : What if the plane has one even side? As it is shown in Figure 2 If the squares m and n with odd sides are set to the plane, one of the distances a or b is odd and since we have used both odd numbers, so it is possible to tile an odd plane with an even set.

Proof 2 : what if both sides in the finite plane are odd? The area will be odd, but if we calculate the area for an even set with two odd numbers, it will be even. So, an even set with two odd numbers can not tile the plane.

2.2 Set With Four or Five Odd Numbers

Till now tiling finite planes with 1, 2 and 3 odd numbers and a set of evens has been covered. The next propositions will cover tiling for $n \geq 4$ odds and a set of evens.

2.2.1 Proposition

Definition: It is possible to tile a finite plane by 4 odd numbers and a set of evens.

Proof: Start with a 32×33 squared rectangle composed of nine squares of sides 1,4,7,8,9,10,14,15,18. This sequence of numbers can tile this finite plane. So the proposition is true.

For $n = 5$ another square with odd side length is needed. If we add 33 to the sequence above, there will be a square tiling for a 33×65 squared rectangle that contains 5 odd numbers and a set of evens.

2.3 Set With 6 Odd Numbers

Till now tiling finite planes with 1, 2 and 3 odd numbers and a set of evens has been covered. The next propositions will cover tiling for $n > 4$ odds and a set of evens.

Figure 4: Tiling Example, 98×65

2.3.1 Proposition

Definition: It is possible to tile a finite plane by 6 odd numbers and a set of evens.

Proof: Start with a 98×65 squared rectangle composed of nine squares of sides 1, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 14, 15, 18, 33, 65. This sequence of numbers can tile this finite plane. So the proposition is true.

Figure 5: Tiling Example, 33×65

2.4 Set With $n \geq 7$ Odd Numbers

THEOREM 1: For $n \geq 7$ the sequence 1, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 14, 15, 18, 33, 65 and then Fibonacci rule sequence starting from 88 can tile a finite plane with $n \geq 7$ odd numbers and a set of evens.

PROOF: Till now, tiling for different values of $1 \leq n \leq 6$ with the following sequences is possible:

$n=4$: 1,4,7,8,9,10,14,15,18

$n=5$: 1,4,7,8,9,10,14,15,18,33

$n=6$: 1,4,7,8,9,10,14,15,18,33,65

From this point on, adding two last numbers in this sequence will give us the next number like the Fibonacci sequence. If next number is odd, then the sequence for the next n is complete and tiling with this sequence is possible. Otherwise, adding two last numbers again, will give us the next number, this number is odd. So the sequence is complete. There is an axiom here: if the last two numbers k, l in the sequence are odd, then the following two numbers are required:

$k + l$ and $l + k + l$

This is just like the Fibonacci sequence rule. Otherwise, if one of k and l is odd and the other is even adding just $k + l$ to the sequence is sufficient. Also, two even numbers except 10, 14 are impossible. So the proof is complete. Note: if a set grows faster than Fibonacci sequence, it is not possible to tile plane with it [1].

3 Discussion and Future Works

In this paper, we were not able to prove or disprove the theory for, whether a set of even numbers with 3 odd numbers can be tiled or not. But we proved that if we have a set of even numbers and n odd numbers [1] and the plane is bounded, it is possible to tile the plane. But we have the same question for infinite planes. It has been proved for $n = \{1, 2, 3\}$ in [1] but it is yet an open problem for $n = 3$.

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